

Synthesis of Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds : Part—1.

Synthesis of 2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-aminomethyl-1',3,4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl) quinazol-4(3H)-ones

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The title compounds(IV) have been synthesised with a view to testing their antiparkinsonian activity.

QUINAZOLONE derivatives have been reported to exhibit enhanced central nervous system depressant¹⁻³, anticonvulsant^{4,5}, muscle relaxant^{6,7}, and antiparkinsonian properties⁸. Further, the effectiveness of 1,3,4-thiadiazole in parkinsonism has also been reported⁹. Since parkinsonism is a chronic malady of the central nervous system and most of the synthetic drugs which are recommended in this condition, are either antihistaminic or anti-cholinergics, authors, therefore, were prompted to prepare the compounds having the benzoxazinone (Ib) and thiadiazole(Ia) nuclei, and to study their pharmacological effects.

II, R = H

III, R = Br

obtained which was filtered and treated with sodium-bi-carbonate soln. (5%) to remove unreacted acid. The product (Ib) was collected by filtration, and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-methyl-1',-3', 4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones(II) :

A mixture of an equimolar amounts of appropriate 2-aryl or alkyl benzoxazinone(Ib) (0.1 mole) and 2-amino-5-methyl-1,3,4 thiadiazole¹⁰ in pyridine (15 ml) was heated under reflux on a sand bath for 6 hr under anhydrous conditions. The contents were cooled and acidified with dil. HCl. The precipitated material was filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol. The various *quinazolones*(II) thus synthesized are listed in Table 1.

TABLE—1

2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-methyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones(II)

R'	Molecular formula	Melting point °C	N% Analysis	
			Calculated	Found
CH ₃ -	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO	182	21.70	21.21
C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ SO	118	17.5	17.08
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ SO	208-209	16.18	15.65

2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-bromomethyl-1', 3',-4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones(III) :

Bromine (about 0.02 moles) was added dropwise with constant stirring to a well cooled solution of the quinazolone(II) (0.1 mole) in acetic acid

TABLE—2

2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-bromomethyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazole-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones(III)

R'	Molecular formula	Melting point °C	N% Analysis	
			Calculated	Found
BrCH ₂ -	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₄ SO Br ₂	280-281	13.46	13.00
C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₄ SO Br	232	14.08	13.56
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ SO Br	165	13.17	12.69

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries in conc. sulphuric acid bath, and are uncorrected.

2-Aryl/alkyl¹¹-benzoxazinones(Ib) :

A solution of anthranilic acid (0.1 mole) in minimum quantity of pyridine (15 ml) was cooled. The appropriate acid chloride (0.2 mole) was added dropwise with constant stirring. A solid mass was

TABLE 3—2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-aminomethyl-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones (IV)

R'	R''	R'''	Molecular Formula	Melting Point °C	N% Analysis	
					Calculated	Found
C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ SO	175	7.90	17.47
C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -	CH ₃ -	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ SO	230	19.28	19.50
C ₆ H ₅ -	-CH ₂ CH ₂ -NHCH ₃ -CH ₃ -	-	C ₂₆ H ₁₀ N ₁₀ S ₂ O ₂	288-239	19.89	19.09
C ₆ H ₅ -	-CH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₃ -	-	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₅ SO ₂	205	17.28	17.00
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ N ₅ SO	205	16.78	16.29
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ SO	158-159	13.64	13.80
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	C ₆ H ₅ -	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₅ SO	142	16.01	15.51
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	o-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ N ₅ SO	112	15.52	15.05
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-	-CH ₂ CH ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₃ -	-	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ N ₅ SO ₂	150	16.24	16.50
o-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NHCH ₃ -	o-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	H	C ₂₀ H ₉ N ₅ SO	272	17.94	18.00
p-CH ₂ O-C ₆ H ₄ NHCH ₃ -	p-CH ₂ O-C ₆ H ₄ -	H	C ₂₀ H ₉ N ₅ SO ₂	288	16.80	16.45

(15 ml). The desired product (III) was obtained on pouring the reaction mixture into crushed ice. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

2-Aryl/alkyl-3-(2'-methyl amino-1', 3', 4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl)-quinazol-4(3H)-ones (IV) :

A mixture of appropriate bromoproduct(III) (0.1 mole) and amine (0.1 mole) in ethanol was refluxed on sand bath for 2 hr. The resultant reaction mixture was cooled, and acidified *quinolone* (III) with dil. HCl. The solid deposited was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 3).

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